

1 **Occupational lead exposure in gasoline station forecourt attendants and**
2 **other occupations in relation to ALS (amyotrophic lateral sclerosis) risk**

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26 **Abstract**

27 Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is an always fatal neurodegenerative disease
28 characterised by a gradual death of motor neurons in the spinal cord and brain. The
29 cause of ALS is unknown. A number of occupations are associated with elevated risks
30 for both ALS and lead (Pb) exposure, indicating a possible connection between these
31 two risks. Gasoline station forecourt attendants, also known as petrol station
32 assistants, show one of the highest occupational ALS risks ever calculated, i.e. OR
33 8.31; 95% CI 1.79 to 38.54. Here, we investigated blood concentrations of Pb in petrol
34 station forecourt attendants (n=38) and a control group (n=36). Participants were
35 divided into groups based on number of years worked. A questionnaire was designed
36 to investigate the health status and work-related lifestyle habits of the participants.
37 Blood samples were collected by medical professionals and analysed for Pb
38 concentration by ICP-MS. A positive correlation between number of years worked
39 and Pb blood concentrations was observed in the petrol station forecourt attendants.
40 The Pb blood levels were also influenced by smoking. Because Pb appears to be a risk
41 factor for ALS, we argue that work exposure to Pb from gasoline could partially
42 explain the increased ALS risk among forecourt attendants,

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47 **1. Introduction**

48 *1.1 Background and risk factors of ALS*

49 Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is an always fatal neurodegenerative disease
50 characterised by a gradual death of motor neurons in the spinal cord and brain [1].
51 Worldwide ALS incidence is some 2/100,000 and prevalence 3-5 per 100,000
52 inhabitants [1], with a significant geographical variation [2]. ALS is characterised by
53 muscle weakness and atrophy leading to respiratory failure and death on average 3
54 years after disease onset, with a wide variation in survival time [3]. A family history of
55 ALS can be found in about 10% of cases [4]. Some 30 various gene-associations have
56 so far been identified within this group [5]. Genome-wide association studies have
57 shown a possible genetic component of about 21 % in ALS [6]. When every case of
58 ALS is considered, the genetic influence on sporadic ALS can be described as weak
59 [7]. In the light of these conclusions, environmental risk factors for ALS need attention
60 [8].

61

62 Various occupational exposures have been explored as preceding events leading to
63 ALS [9]. Interestingly, many of these occupations involve exposure to lead (Pb),
64 indicating a possible connection between ALS and Pb exposure. Examples of such
65 occupations with Pb exposure are military service occupations [10, 11], constructions
66 workers [12, 13], mechanical workers [14, 15], precision tool manufacturers, and glass,
67 pottery, and tile workers [11]. All these occupations have also been associated with an
68 increased ALS risk [10-15]. A connection between occupational Pb exposure and

69 elevated ALS risk can furthermore be found for leather workers [16] and tanners [17,
70 18]. Farmers show an elevated ALS risk [19, 20], and farming exposes the farm workers
71 to pesticides and insecticides [21, 22]. Many insecticides have been Pb compounds,
72 especially older preparations in heavy use until the 1960's, and lead arsenate
73 (PbHAsO_4) was often prepared by the farm workers themselves by reacting soluble
74 lead salts with sodium arsenate (NaH_2AsO_4) [23]. Lead arsenate as an insecticide was
75 withdrawn in 1988 [23].

76

77 Gasoline station forecourt attendants, also known as petrol station assistants, filling
78 station petrol dispensing attendants, fuel pump filling workers, or simply fuel station
79 workers, have previously been shown to have one of the highest occupational ALS
80 risks ever calculated, i.e. OR 8.31; 95% CI 1.79 to 38.54 [24]. No explanation has so
81 far been provided for this elevated ALS risk among fuel station workers. Here, we
82 report elevated Pb concentrations in blood from forecourt attendants in South Africa,
83 and discuss how this finding strengthens the hypothesis that ALS is induced by Pb
84 exposure.

85

86 *1.2 ALS in gasoline station forecourt attendants*

87 An extensive population-based study on the association between occupation and ALS
88 risk was conducted in New Zealand between the years 2013 and 2016 [24]. In a case-
89 control design 321 cases of ALS were compared to 605 controls randomly selected
90 from the Electoral Roll. Occupational history and duration of employment was
91 collected through questionnaires and interviews. An elevated ALS risk was noted for

92 several occupations such as farmers, fishery workers, hunters, trappers, electricians,
93 and telecommunications technicians [24]. The common denominator for these varied
94 occupations remains to be elucidated. The highest odds ratio (OR) for ALS risk was
95 calculated for the job title classification 52113 i.e. forecourt attendants (OR 8.31, 95%
96 CI 1.79 to 38.54). This OR is 2-3 times higher than any other occupation with elevated
97 ALS risk in this large study, and the upper limit of the confidence interval reaches OR
98 38 even though this OR is based on only 11 cases [24]. These statistics should be seen
99 in perspective of the low ALS prevalence in New Zealand, i.e. 2.3/100000 [25]. Prior
100 to the New Zealand study on Motor Neurone Disease Association [24], petrol station
101 forecourt attendants were not included with their own code in the New Zealand
102 classification of occupations. Before this re-classification, the specific exposure to Pb
103 from gasoline might have been spread out over other occupational classes, making an
104 ALS risk OR of 8.31 for forecourt attendants even more exceptional. A slightly lower
105 risk, but still high, was documented for the job title G5321 i.e. automotive fuel
106 retailing [24]. It can therefore be suspected that exposure to automotive fuel, e.g.
107 gasoline/petrol, is responsible for the increased ALS risks among both gasoline station
108 forecourt attendants and automotive fuel retailers. This possibility is supported by
109 another more recent study from New Zealand, which showed that occupational
110 exposure to gasoline was associated with an elevated (OR=2.24) risk for ALS [26].

111

112

113 **2. Materials and Methods**

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115

116 ***2.1 Participants***

117 The study participants (n=74) lived in Gauteng, a suburb to Pretoria in South Africa.

118 The study involved 38 adult individuals who were either currently or previously

119 employed as gasoline station forecourt attendants. This group was divided into

120 subgroups based on years of service, as shown in Table 1. As controls served 36

121 individuals who did not have any contact with petrol on a daily basis, i.e. students or

122 workers who lived far away from any of the studied petrol stations, and who reached

123 their workplace on foot. A written form for informed consent was signed by all

124 participants, who filled out a structured questionnaire, with details on occupation,

125 health status, smoking habits, and sociodemographic status. Ethical approval for the

126 project was provided by the Sefako Makgatho Health Sciences Research Committee

127 (SMUREC/S/91/2020:PG and SMUREC/S/92/2020:PG). The recruitment period for

128 the blood sampling and the questionnaire was 6 Aug 2020 - 14 Dec 2021.

129

130 ***2.2 Working conditions for gasoline station forecourt attendants in Pretoria***

131 In South Africa, the daily duties of the forecourt attendants are important to the

132 management of the gasoline station, as they represent the station business

133 establishment and as such have certain obligations. This job is about to disappear as

134 self-service is spreading at gas stations over the world, however in South Africa

135 traditionally the attendant provides manual service by walking out to each vehicle and

136 fuelling it. No protective devices are used between the car gasoline tank and the open

137 air during filling, and the attendants are therefore frequently inhaling gasoline vapour.

138 Along with dispensing gasoline, the employees check the tire pressure, oil and water
139 in the vehicles. Some gasoline stations in South Africa are open for 24 hours, and
140 work shifts are split between employees to meet all hours. A typical shift for a
141 gasoline station forecourt attendant lasts about 8 hours, but supervisory staff members
142 may work up to 12 hours.

143

144 ***2.3 Analysis of metal concentrations***

145 Methods and steps for collecting the blood samples and analysing their concentrations
146 of Pb have been described previously [27]. In short, blood was collected from an
147 antecubital vein of each participant by qualified health workers from Dr. George
148 Mukhari Academic Hospital Pretoria, using established procedures. The blood
149 samples were digested by 0.5% HCl and 1.5% HNO₃ in purified water. The digested
150 sample was then diluted with an internal standard solution, centrifuged, and Pb
151 concentrations in the supernatants measured with an Agilent 7700 series inductively
152 coupled plasma mass spectrometry instrument [28]. The blood sample analysis was
153 conducted by an accredited laboratory in South Africa, where the samples were
154 analysed in triplicate using ClinChek® certified reference materials. The Limit of
155 Detection (LOD) was 0.2 µg/L, and the Limit of Quantification (LOQ) was 0.6 µg/L
156 [27].

157

158 Statistical analysis was performed with the SPSS 28.0 statistical software. One-way
159 ANOVA tests were used to determine if the differences in Pb concentrations between

160 different study groups were statistically significant or not. The level of statistical
161 significance was set to $p < 0.05$.

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163

164 **3. Results**

165 Blood Pb concentrations of petrol station forecourt attendants, number of years worked,
166 and lifestyle habits associated with the work situation, are presented in Tables 1–3 and
167 Fig. 1. The blood Pb concentrations uniformly increased with number of years worked
168 (Fig. 1), and the difference between the group with 11 or more years of service (Pb =
169 24.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$) and the group with 1-3 years of service (Pb = 10.4 $\mu\text{g/L}$) is statistically
170 significant ($p < 0.05$). These values have previously been reported [27], and are here
171 reprinted in Table 1.

172

173 Table 2 shows that the blood Pb concentrations were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in
174 forecourt attendants who are smokers (Pb = 19.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$) compared to non-smokers (Pb
175 = 10.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$). This is not unexpected, as it is well known that tobacco products and
176 tobacco smoke contain toxic metals, mainly cadmium but also Pb [29-31].

177

178 Lifestyle habits of the forecourt attendants are shown in Table 3. Most of the
179 participants (92%) changed their uniforms after working one or two shifts, but 8% did
180 not. It can be assumed that some petrol products are spilled onto the uniform during a
181 normal workday, and re-using a dirty uniform will therefore increase the dermal
182 exposure to petroleum products. Similarly, the 11% of the forecourt attendants that do

183 not shower after work will likely suffer more dermal exposure to petroleum than the
184 89% that do shower (Table 3). Around half of the participants (45%) lived in the same
185 area where they worked, and these are likely the same 45% of participants who
186 walked to their jobs (Table 3). The remaining 55% of participants commuted to their
187 workplaces via public transportation (52%) or with their own car (3%), thereby
188 exposing themselves to bus and car exhaust fumes, which are known to contain
189 harmful chemicals. For example, elevated Pb concentrations have been reported in the
190 blood of bus drivers in Indonesia [32].

191

192

193 **4. Discussion**

194 Our measurements on forecourt attendants in South Africa [27] show that their blood
195 Pb concentrations significantly increase with the number of years worked (Table 1;
196 Fig. 1). This strongly suggests that the underlying Pb exposure is work-related.
197 However, other factors such as cigarette smoking [31] also contribute to Pb exposure
198 (Table 2), and work-related life-style habits (Table 3) do influence the amount of Pb
199 exposure at work. These results are not surprising, as earlier studies have found
200 significantly elevated blood Pb concentrations in fuel station workers in Iraq [33], India
201 [34], Nigeria [35], Sudan [36] and Iran [37].

202

203 The work-related Pb exposure most certainly derives from Pb in gasoline. During the
204 20th century, external Pb was often added to gasoline to improve the performance of
205 combustion engines [38]. The use of Pb additives has gradually been phased out, and as

206 a result blood Pb concentrations have decreased worldwide [38]. In 2021, Algeria
207 became the last country on the planet to ban Pb additives in automobile gasoline [38]. In
208 South Africa, such Pb additives were banned in 2006 [27]. However, in many countries
209 Pb is still used as an additive in fuel for aeroplanes, off-road motorbikes, racing cars,
210 and military vehicles. Furthermore, non-leaded gasoline still contains small amounts of
211 intrinsic Pb, together with trace amounts of other metals such as iron and zinc [39]. This
212 intrinsic Pb, which can be differentiated from added Pb by isotope separation, should
213 not be ignored as it can contribute significant amounts of Pb to the environment [39, 40].

214

215 Lead in petrol fumes is likely inhaled into the lung alveoli and to some extent
216 deposited in the lungs. However, the majority of Pb passes the alveolar endothelium
217 and capillary endothelium into the bloodstream. Such respiratory exposure must be the
218 main Pb exposure route for forecourt attendants, even though Pb can also pass the skin
219 barrier and enter the bloodstream directly after dermal exposure [41]. Pb is then
220 transported in the blood tightly bound to haemoglobin in red blood cells [42] and
221 distributed to every organ system, although mostly kidneys, liver and bone [41]. In
222 adults, Pb is to 90 % stored in bone [43], from where it can re-enter into the circulation
223 in response to changes in bone mineralization [44].

224

225 Pb is a well-known neurotoxic metal [41] that should be considered an established risk
226 factor for ALS [8, 45-48]. The high Pb concentrations in blood of experienced forecourt
227 attendants (Fig 1; Table 1) may therefore explain their higher ALS risk. This would be
228 consistent with the observation that some of the earliest described ALS cases were

229 related to Pb exposure [49-51]. In fact, long-time low-dose Pb exposure produces a
230 clinical picture indistinguishable from ALS [52, 53]. Yet, few studies have investigated
231 gasoline, or specifically Pb in gasoline, as a possible contributing factor in ALS
232 pathogenesis.

233

234 The detailed causes and origins of ALS remain unknown, and little is known about the
235 molecular mechanisms that underlie ALS [8]. Still, some observations can be made. For
236 example, some 250,000 tonnes of Pb were emitted from gasoline in Australia between
237 1933 and 2002, i.e. until leaded automobile gasoline was banned [54]. Lifetime Pb
238 exposure from this gasoline was found to be associated with age-specific ALS death
239 rates [54]. A related study [55] used linear regression models to estimate a temporal
240 association between accumulated gasoline lead emissions and ALS in Australia; the
241 best fit correlation was found between a 20-year lag of gasoline lead emissions and
242 percent all cause ALS death ($R^2 = 0.98$, $p = 2.6 \times 10^{-44}$). This suggests a slow
243 mechanism where Pb from chronic exposure accumulates over time, eventually
244 triggering ALS pathology.

245

246 Blood Pb is known to reach the cerebral arteries, arterioles and capillaries, where it
247 can traverse the capillary endothelia which constitute the blood-brain barrier into the
248 cerebral interstitial fluid [56]. Alternatively, blood Pb can directly pass the blood-CSF
249 barrier at the level of the choroid plexus into the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) which
250 surrounds the cerebral cortex and the spinal cord. Lead concentrations in CSF are
251 normally low, but Pb can accumulate in the peripheral nervous system in exposed

252 individuals [41]. Lead is classified as a selective choroid plexus toxicant, and Pb
253 accumulates to a great extent in the choroid plexus [57, 58] and disturbs its barrier
254 functions [58].

255

256 Spinal cord anterior horn motor neurons, the nerve cells primarily affected in ALS,
257 seem to be specifically vulnerable to Pb toxicity [49, 59-61] and to selenite toxicity [62,
258 63]. The details regarding how Pb could contribute to ALS are unclear, and several
259 mechanisms are possible. For example, Pb ions do induce oxidative stress, mimic
260 other metal ions, and modulate the aggregation of harmful amyloid proteins such as
261 amyloid- β [31] and possibly TDP-43 as well [64]. In evaluating the direct toxic effects
262 of Pb on the anterior horn cells of the spinal cord in ALS patients, the actual blood Pb
263 concentration itself might be less important than the concentration ratios between Pb
264 and other neurotoxic and/or protective metals [65] that could contribute to synergistic
265 or attenuating effects in relation to Pb.

266

267 It should be pointed out that gasoline/petrol is a liquid that mainly consists of
268 hydrocarbons in the form of alkanes, alkenes, and aromatic components. Many of these
269 hydrocarbons are neurotoxic and/or carcinogenic [66, 67], and might contribute to
270 neurodegenerative diseases including ALS [31, 68]. The possible mechanisms are
271 unclear. One study found that organic molecules such as aromatics and dioxins that bind
272 to the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AHR), increase production of TDP-43 [69], a protein
273 that appears to be involved in ALS pathology [64, 70, 71]. Thus, Pb may not be the only
274 ALS risk factor in gasoline/petrol.

275

276 Other toxic effects of Pb also need consideration, as lead affects both the central and
277 the peripheral nervous systems. In the peripheral nervous system variable presentation
278 of Pb neuropathy has been recognized [72]. However, in contrast to most other toxic
279 neuropathies, Pb causes a subacute, predominantly motor neuropathy with early
280 involvement of the wrist and finger extensors [73]. This classical form of motor only
281 Pb neuropathy is most commonly seen after occupational Pb exposure, and probably
282 never occurs at blood Pb concentrations below 80 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ [73]. The possible spinal
283 origin of Pb neuropathy, as in ALS, following chronic low dose Pb intoxications has
284 been debated for more than a century [61, 74, 75]. The historical observations from a
285 series of more than a thousand Pb-intoxicated patients stating the anterior horn of the
286 spinal cord as the primary site of injury, are still valid [75].

287

288 Furthermore, even low Pb doses are hazardous [76], and they can induce neuronal
289 damage that lead to lower intelligence quotient (IQ) levels, where a non-linear dose-
290 response relationship exists between IQ reduction and amount of Pb exposure [77, 78].
291 For example, reduced IQ has been documented in children with blood Pb
292 concentrations as low as 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$, where an increase in blood lead from 2.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ to
293 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ was associated with a decrement of 3.9 IQ points [79].

294

295 In the coming decades, we expect to observe reduced Pb exposure risk and hence
296 reduced ALS incidence in forecourt attendants, due to both the removal of Pb
297 additives in automobile gasoline and to the increasing number of self-service fuel

298 stations across the world. High alert and vigilance towards other sources of Pb
299 exposure and other exposure routes is recommend.

300

301 **5. Conclusion**

302 Exposure to lead from gasoline could partially explain the previously reported
303 elevated ALS risk for gasoline forecourt attendants.

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310 **Author contributions**

311 Conceptualization, J.O.O and P.M.R.; methodology, J.O.O, P.M.R., S.K.T.S.W. and

312 U.A.T; validation, L.K., P.M.R., S.K.T.S.W. and U.A.T.; formal analysis, A.S.K.,

313 N.G.L., L.L.M., P.M.R., S.K.T.S.W. and U.A.T.; investigation, A.S.K., N.G.L.,

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315 A.S.K., N.G.L., S.K.T.S.W. and U.A.T.; writing-original draft preparation, L.K,

316 P.M.R. and S.K.T.S.W.; writing-review and editing, J.O.O and P.M.R.; visualization,

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324

325 **Data availability**

326 All datasets generated and/or analysed during the current study are included in the
327 manuscript.

328

329 **Conflicts of interest**

330 The authors declare no conflict of interest. SW is a shareholder in the company CellPept
331 Sweden AB. Neither this company, nor the funding organizations, had any role in the
332 design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing
333 of the manuscript; or in the decision to publish the results.

334

335 **Keywords**

336 Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, occupational exposure; petrol; fuel; Pb; petrol station
337 assistant; fuel station worker; filling station petrol dispensing attendant;
338 neurodegeneration

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589 Figures and tables

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592 **Figure 1.** Pb concentrations ($\mu\text{g/L}$) in blood (mean \pm standard deviation) from
593 forecourt attendants in relation to number of years worked. Based on data in Table 1,
594 originating from reference: [27].

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597 **Table 1.** Pb concentrations ($\mu\text{g/L}$) in blood from forecourt attendants in relation to
598 number of years worked. Based on data in reference [27].

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean \pm SD
2-5 years of service	5.21	28.5	10.4 \pm 5.4
6-10 years of service	5.04	23.8	12.6 \pm 5.1
11-20 and more years of service	12.4	60.2	24.5 \pm 18.2
Control group	4.37	41.3	16.9 \pm 9.2

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606 **Table 2.** Pb concentrations ($\mu\text{g/L}$) in blood from forecourt attendants who are smokers
607 and non-smokers, respectively.

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean \pm SD
Non-smokers	5.04	15.8	10.2 \pm 3.8
Smokers	5.04	60.2	19.5 \pm 13.9

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610 **Table 3.** Lifestyle habits associated with the work situation of forecourt attendants.

Lifestyle habits		N=38
Uniform change	1 wear	16 (42%)
	2 wears	19 (50%)
	3 wears	2 (5%)
	After a week	1 (3%)
Shower after work	Yes	34 (89%)
	No	4 (11%)
Live in the area	Yes	17 (45%)
	No	21 (55%)
Transportation	Own car	1 (3%)
	Public transport	20 (52%)
	Walking	17 (45%)

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